

STUDYING THE EFFECT OF NON-RESPONSE ON IMPROVED ESTIMATORS AND THEIR EFFICIENCY IN THE PRESENCE OF SIMULTANEOUS NON-RESPONSE AND MEASUREMENT ERRORS

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ABSTRACT

In survey sampling, it is a common practice that two non-sampling errors do occur during collection of survey data. These errors are the non-response and measurement errors. Non-response error is the most serious error in survey sampling. Estimation strategies such as Ratio, Product and Regression methods are influenced by these errors. Also, the properties of these estimators are influenced significantly. So, to obtaining estimators that are less affected by these errors is a challenging task. It is the responsibility of the researcher(s) to develop estimators that are less affected by these errors to obtain more valid, reliable and efficient estimators. In this paper, existing improved mean estimators studied under the influence of measurement errors alone will be restudied under the effect of non-response alone and their efficiency in the presence of non-response and measurement errors. The properties (Biases and mean square errors) were derived up to first order approximation using Taylor series method. A numerical study was conducted to ascertain the performance of the proposed estimators under the effect of non-response and measurement errors and the result revealed that the proposed estimators are efficient.

Keywords: Estimate, Estimation, Measurement Errors, Non-response, Survey

1.0 Introduction

Data collected from survey are assumed to be correct and are used to calculate the statistics such as mean, median, standard deviation, etc of characteristic of population under study. But this assumption is not true in reality. It is a fact the data collected during survey are contaminated with non-response and measurement errors. Non-response and Measurement errors are two common problematic errors that exist during the conduct of surveys that involve human population. Non-response errors occur when selected participants do not respond or refuse to participate in a survey. Estimation strategies such as Ratio, Product and Regression method will be greatly affected by non-response errors and produced unreliable estimate of the population parameters, such population mean, variance, etc. Authors have made tremendous work by developing estimators in the presence on non-response errors for reliable estimates, they include: Hansen and Hurwitz (1946), Khare and Srivastava (1993), Adejumobi et al. (2022), Audu et al. (2021a,b), Musa et al. (2023), etc.

Measurement errors arise from inaccurate or imprecise measurements such as: respondents' errors meaning, misunderstanding questions or providing incorrect answers; interviewer errors, that is, influencing respondents' answers or recording errors; Instrument errors, flawed survey questions or tools. Measurement errors are errors obtained when there is a deviation between the true value and observed value of a variable. Estimation strategies such as Ratio, Product

and Regression method will be greatly affected by measurement errors and produced unreliable estimate of the population parameters, such population mean, variance, etc. Authors have made tremendous efforts by developing estimators in the presence on measurement errors for reliable estimates, they include: Shalabh (1997), Malik and Singh (2013), Alafara et al. (2025), etc.

It has been established by authors that auxiliary information improves estimation strategies, and that both non-response and measurement errors have great effect on the properties of the estimators. The effects of non-response and measurement errors on estimators can results to: (i) Bias estimate, that is, it lead to inaccurate representation of the population, (ii) increase variance or mean square errors, (iii) it reduces the precision or accuracy of estimates, (iv) Affect validity, that is, compromise the surveys' overall validity and reliability. To minimize these errors in estimation, the following measures can be taken, pilot testing, multiple contact attempts, data validation and statistical adjustment. Authors have proposed efficient estimators in the presence of non-response and measurement errors, they include: Singh and Sharma (2015), Sigh et al. (2020), Audu et al. (2023), Abubakar et al. (2024), etc., in this current study, we intend studying the effect of non-response on the estimators proposed by Alafara et al. (2025) under measurement errors in comparison with existing estimators in the presence of non-response and measurement errors.

1.1 Statistical notations used in the study

$S_Y^2 = (N-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2$: is the population mean square of Y

$S_{Y(2)}^2 = (N_2-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_2} (Y_{(2)i} - \bar{Y}_2)^2$: is the population mean square of Y_2

$S_X^2 = (N-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^2$: is the population mean square of X

$S_{X(2)}^2 = (N_2-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_2} (X_{(2)i} - \bar{X}_2)^2$: is the population mean square of X_2

$S_{YX} = (N-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (Y_i - \bar{Y})(X_i - \bar{X})$: is the population covariance of Y and X

$S_{YX(2)} = (N-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (Y_{(2)i} - \bar{Y}_2)(X_{(2)i} - \bar{X}_2)$: is the population covariance of Y_2 and X_2

$S_U^2 = (N-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N e_{yi}^{*2}$: is the population mean square of ME e_y^*

$S_V^2 = (N-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N e_{xi}^{*2}$: is the population mean square of ME e_x^*

$S_{U(2)}^2 = (N_2-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_2} e_{y(2)i}^{*2}$: is the population mean square of ME $e_{y(2)}^*$ from G_{NR}

$S_{V(2)}^2 = (N_2-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_2} e_{x(2)i}^{*2}$: is the population mean square of ME $e_{x(2)}^*$ from G_{NR}

2.0 Literature review

Define Y and X as study and auxiliary variables of population units $Z(Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_N)$ from sample of size n is drawn using SRTSWOR design. Let two non-overlapping subgroups from Z in which units $Y_{(1)i}; i=1, 2, \dots, N_1$ from N is considered as responding group G_R and units $Y_{(2)i}; i=1, 2, \dots, N_2$ is non-responding group G_{NR} such that $\sum_{j=1}^2 N_j = N$. Define n_1 and n_2 as sample sizes from G_R with units $y_{ij}; i=1, 2, \dots, n_1$ and G_{NR} respectively for $\sum_{j=1}^2 n_j = n$. Let a subsample of size h with units $y_{hi}, i=1, 2, \dots, h$ from n_2 is interviewed and responded for $\lambda = n_2 / h$ ($\lambda > 1$). Let x_i^*, y_i^* denote the observed and X_i^*, Y_i^* denote actual values of X, Y respectively from Z , then the measurement errors are given by $e_{yi}^* = y_i^* - Y_i^*$ and $e_{xi}^* = x_i^* - X_i^*$ are unrelated random variables with zero mean and constant variance.

To determine the properties of the proposed estimators in this study, the following relation will be used

$$e_0 = \bar{Y}^{-1}(\bar{y}_e^* - \bar{Y}), \quad e_1 = \bar{X}^{-1}(\bar{x}_e^* - \bar{X}), \quad \text{such that } \bar{y}_e^* = \bar{Y}(1 + e_0), \quad \bar{x}_e^* = \bar{X}(1 + e_1)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E(e_0^2) &= \frac{\pi_1(S_Y^2 + S_U^2) + \pi_2(S_{Y(2)}^2 + S_{U(2)}^2)}{\bar{Y}^2} = \frac{\Delta_0}{\bar{Y}^2} = \Omega_0, \quad E(e_0) = 0 \\ E(e_1^2) &= \frac{\pi_1(S_X^2 + S_V^2) + \pi_2(S_{X(2)}^2 + S_{V(2)}^2)}{\bar{X}^2} = \frac{\Delta_1}{\bar{X}^2} = \Omega_1, \quad E(e_1) = 0 \\ E(e_0 e_1) &= \frac{\pi_1 \rho_{YX} S_Y S_X + \pi_2 \rho_{YX(2)} S_{Y(2)} S_{X(2)}}{\bar{Y} \bar{X}} = \frac{\Delta_2}{\bar{Y} \bar{X}} = \Omega_2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

2.1 Existing mean Estimators with nonresponse and measurement errors in the literature

Hansen and Hurwitz(1946) mean estimator in the simultaneous presence of non-response and measurement errors is given by

$$t_0 = \bar{y}_e^* = n^{-1} \left(n_1 \bar{y}_{1(e)}^* + n_2 \bar{y}_{h(e)}^* \right) \quad (2.1)$$

The variance of the estimator t_0 is given by

$$\text{Var}(t_0) = \pi_1(S_Y^2 + S_U^2) + \pi_2(S_{Y(2)}^2 + S_{U(2)}^2) = \Delta_0 \quad (2.2)$$

Where, $\bar{y}_{1(e)}^* = n_1^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^h y_{1i}^*$, $\bar{y}_{h(e)}^* = h^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^h y_{hi}^*$, $W_2 = N_2 N^{-1}$, $\pi_1 = n^{-1}$, $\pi_1 = n^{-1} W_2 (\lambda - 1)$.

Singh and Sharma (2015) proposed the ratio estimator in the presence of non-response and measurement error as

$$t_{ss1} = \bar{y}_e^* \left(\frac{\bar{X}}{\bar{x}_e^*} \right) \quad (2.3)$$

The mean square error of the estimator is given by

$$MSE(t_{ss1}) = \Delta_0 + R^2 \Delta_1 - 2R\Delta_2 \quad (2.4)$$

Where, $\bar{x}_{1(e)} = n_1^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^h x_{1i}^*$, $\bar{x}_{h(e)} = h^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^h x_{hi}^*$, $W_2 = N_2 N^{-1}$, $\pi_1 = n^{-1}$, $\pi_1 = n^{-1} W_2 (\lambda - 1)$.

Singh and Sharma (2015) proposed linear combination of sample mean estimator and ratio estimator in the presence of non-response and measurement error as

$$t_{ss2} = m_1 \bar{y}_e^* + m_2 \bar{y}_e^* \left(\frac{\bar{X}}{\bar{x}_e^*} \right) \quad (2.5)$$

The minimum mean square error of the estimator is given by

$$MSE(t_{ss2})_{\min} = \Delta_0 - \frac{\Delta_2^2}{\Delta_1} \quad (2.6)$$

Audu et al. (2021) proposed almost unbiased estimators for population mean in the presence of non-response and measurement errors as

$$t_{a1} = \omega_0 \bar{y}_e^* + \omega_1 \bar{y}_e^* \left(\frac{a_x \bar{X} + b_x}{a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x} \right) + \omega_2 \bar{y}_e^* \left(\frac{a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x}{a_x \bar{X} + b_x} \right) \quad (2.7)$$

$$t_{a2} = \phi_0 \bar{y}_e^* + \phi_1 \bar{y}_e^* \left(\frac{a_x \bar{X} + b_x}{a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x} \right) + \phi_2 \bar{y}_e^* \exp \left(\frac{(a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x) - (a_x \bar{X} + b_x)}{(a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x) + (a_x \bar{X} + b_x)} \right) \quad (2.8)$$

$$t_{a3} = \eta_0 \bar{y}_e^* + \eta_1 \bar{y}_e^* \exp \left(\frac{(a_x \bar{X} + b_x) - (a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x)}{(a_x \bar{X} + b_x) + (a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x)} \right) + \eta_2 \bar{y}_e^* \exp \left(\frac{(a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x) - (a_x \bar{X} + b_x)}{(a_x \bar{x}_e^* + b_x) + (a_x \bar{X} + b_x)} \right) \quad (2.9)$$

The minimum mean square error of the estimators are given by

$$MSE(t_{ai})_{\min} = \Delta_0 - \frac{\Delta_2^2}{\Delta_1}, i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (2.10)$$

Where, a_x, b_x are parameters of X such coefficient of variation, kurtosis, skewness, etc.

3 Proposed Estimators

Having studied the estimators of Alafara et al. (2025) in the presence of measurement errors, we intend to study the effect of non-response on their estimators and also study the efficiency of their estimators under simultaneous influence of non-response and measurement errors with estimators in the literature. The proposed estimators in the presence of non-response and measurement errors are

$$t_{p1} = (w_1 + 1)\bar{y}_e^* + w_2 \exp\left(\frac{\bar{X} - \bar{x}_e^*}{\bar{X} + \bar{x}_e^*}\right) \quad (3.1)$$

$$t_{p2} = (r_1 + 1)\bar{y}_e^* + r_2 \frac{\bar{X}}{\bar{x}_e^* - \bar{X}} \ln\left(\frac{\bar{x}_e^*}{\bar{X}}\right) \quad (3.2)$$

$$t_{p3} = (k_1 + 1)\bar{y}_e^* + 2^{-1}k_2 \left\{ \left(\frac{\bar{X}}{\bar{x}_e^*}\right) + \exp\left(\frac{\bar{X} - \bar{x}_e^*}{\bar{X} + \bar{x}_e^*}\right) \right\} \quad (3.3)$$

$$t_{p4} = (a_1 + 1)\bar{y}_e^* + 2^{-1}a_2 \left\{ \left(\frac{\bar{X}}{\bar{x}_e^*}\right) + \frac{\bar{X}}{\bar{x}_e^* - \bar{X}} \ln\left(\frac{\bar{x}_e^*}{\bar{X}}\right) \right\} \quad (3.4)$$

3.1 Mean square errors (MSEs) of Estimators $t_{p1}, t_{p2}, t_{p3}, t_{p4}$

To obtain the mean square error of the estimator t_{p1} , we express estimator t_{p1} in terms of sampling errors defined in (1.1) as

$$t_{p1} = (w_1 + 1)\bar{Y}(1 + e_0) + w_2 \exp\left(\frac{\bar{X} - \bar{X}(1 + e_1)}{\bar{X} + \bar{X}(1 + e_1)}\right) \quad (3.5)$$

Simplifying the exponent part, we have

$$t_{p1} = (w_1 + 1)\bar{Y}(1 + e_0) + w_2 \exp\left(\frac{-e_1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{e_1}{2}\right)^{-1}\right) \quad (3.6)$$

Simplifying (3.6) further, we obtained (3.7)

$$t_{p1} = \bar{Y} \left[1 + e_0 + w_1(1 + e_0) + \frac{w_2}{\bar{Y}} \left(1 - \frac{e_1}{2} + \frac{3e_1^2}{8} \right) \right] \quad (3.7)$$

Subtracting \bar{Y} from both sides of (3.7), we obtained (3.8)

$$t_{p1} - \bar{Y} = \bar{Y} \left[e_0 + w_1(1 + e_0) + \frac{w_2}{\bar{Y}} \left(1 - \frac{e_1}{2} + \frac{3e_1^2}{8} \right) \right] \quad (3.8)$$

Squaring and taking expectation on both sides of (3.8) to obtain the mean square error of estimator t_{p1} as

$$MSE(t_{p1}) = \bar{Y}^2 \left[A_0 + w_1^2 B_0 + w_2^2 C_0 + 2w_1 D_0 + 2w_2 E_0 + 2w_1 w_2 F_0 \right] \quad (3.9)$$

$$\text{Where, } A_0 = \Omega_0, B_0 = (1 + \Omega_0), C_0 = \bar{Y}^{-2} (1 + \Omega_1), D_0 = A_0, E_0 = -\frac{1}{2\bar{Y}} \Omega_2, F_0 = \frac{1}{\bar{Y}} \left(1 + \frac{3\Omega_1}{8} - \frac{\Omega_2}{2} \right)$$

By partially differentiating (3.9) with respect to w_1 and w_2 , we obtained

$$w_1 = \frac{E_0 F_0 - C_0 D_0}{B_0 C_0 - F_0^2} \quad \text{and} \quad w_2 = \frac{D_0 F_0 - B_0 E_0}{B_0 C_0 - F_0^2}$$

Similarly, following the same approach for (3.2), (3.3) and (3.4), the mean square errors of estimators t_{p2} , t_{p3} , and t_{p4} are

$$MSE(t_{p2}) = \bar{Y}^2 \left[A_1 + r_1^2 B_1 + r_2^2 C_1 + 2r_1 D_1 + 2r_2 E_1 + 2r_1 r_2 F_1 \right] \quad (3.10)$$

$$MSE(t_{p3}) = \bar{Y}^2 \left[A_2 + k_1^2 B_2 + k_2^2 C_2 + 2k_1 D_2 + 2k_2 E_2 + 2k_1 k_2 F_2 \right] \quad (3.11)$$

$$MSE(t_{p4}) = \bar{Y}^2 \left[A_3 + a_1^2 B_3 + a_2^2 C_3 + 2a_1 D_3 + 2a_2 E_3 + 2a_1 a_2 F_3 \right] \quad (3.12)$$

$$\text{Where, } A_1 = A_2 = A_3 = D_1 = D_2 = D_3 = A_0, B_1 = B_2 = B_3 = B_0, E_1 = E_0, E_3 = E_4 = \frac{-3\Omega_2}{4\bar{Y}},$$

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{\bar{Y}} (1 + \Omega_1 - \Omega_2), F_2 = \frac{1}{\bar{Y}} \left(1 + \frac{11\Omega_1}{16} - \frac{3\Omega_2}{4} \right), F_3 = \frac{1}{\bar{Y}} \left(1 + \frac{2\Omega_1}{3} - \frac{3\Omega_2}{4} \right), r_1 = \frac{E_1 F_1 - C_1 D_1}{B_1 C_1 - F_1^2},$$

$$r_2 = \frac{D_1 F_1 - B_1 E_1}{B_1 C_1 - F_1^2}, k_1 = \frac{E_2 F_2 - C_2 D_2}{B_2 C_2 - F_2^2}, k_2 = \frac{D_2 F_2 - B_2 E_2}{B_2 C_2 - F_2^2}, a_1 = \frac{E_3 F_3 - C_3 D_3}{B_3 C_3 - F_3^2}, a_2 = \frac{D_3 F_3 - B_3 E_3}{B_3 C_3 - F_3^2}$$

4. Empirical Study

To investigate the effect of non-response on the existing and proposed estimators as well as the efficiency of the proposed estimators in the presence of non-response and measurement errors, the following population datasets were used.

Population 1: (Source: Audu et al. (2021))

$$N = 5000, N_1 = 4500, N_2 = 500, n = 100, n_1 = 90, n_2 = 10, \bar{Y} = 4.9271, \bar{X} = 4.9243,$$

$$S_Y^2 = 102.007, S_X^2 = 101.411, S_U^2 = 8.8261, S_V^2 = 9.0013, \rho_{YX} = 0.995, S_{Y(2)}^2 = 99.99174,$$

$$S_{X(2)}^2 = 99.8747, S_{U(2)}^2 = 9.1505, S_{V(2)}^2 = 8.756, \rho_{YX(2)} = 0.9949, h = 2$$

Population 2: (Source: Audu et al. (2021))

$$N = 5000, N_1 = 4500, N_2 = 500, n = 100, n_1 = 90, n_2 = 10, \bar{Y} = 4.9271, \bar{X} = 4.9243, \\ S_Y^2 = 102.007, S_X^2 = 101.411, S_U^2 = 8.8261, S_V^2 = 9.0013, \rho_{YX} = 0.995, S_{Y(2)}^2 = 99.99174, \\ S_{X(2)}^2 = 99.8747, S_{U(2)}^2 = 9.1505, S_{V(2)}^2 = 8.756, \rho_{YX(2)} = 0.9949, h = 5$$

Population 3: (Source: Audu et al. (2021))

$$N = 5000, N_1 = 4000, N_2 = 1000, n = 100, n_1 = 80, n_2 = 20, \bar{Y} = 1.96, \bar{X} = 1.9433, \\ S_Y^2 = 25.441, S_X^2 = 100.228, S_U^2 = 6.0404, S_V^2 = 6.2244, \rho_{YX} = 0.9808, S_{Y(2)}^2 = 25.877, \\ S_{X(2)}^2 = 25.213, S_{U(2)}^2 = 5.9383, S_{V(2)}^2 = 6.2722, \rho_{YX(2)} = 0.9825, h = 2$$

Population 4: (Source: Audu et al. (2021))

$$N = 5000, N_1 = 4000, N_2 = 1000, n = 100, n_1 = 80, n_2 = 20, \bar{Y} = 1.96, \bar{X} = 1.9433, \\ S_Y^2 = 25.441, S_X^2 = 100.228, S_U^2 = 6.0404, S_V^2 = 6.2244, \rho_{YX} = 0.9808, S_{Y(2)}^2 = 25.877, \\ S_{X(2)}^2 = 25.213, S_{U(2)}^2 = 5.9383, S_{V(2)}^2 = 6.2722, \rho_{YX(2)} = 0.9825, h = 5$$

Table 1: MSE of Existing and Proposed Estimators in presence of ME, and NR, and Effect of Non-response on the Estimators using population 1

Estimators	MSE (ME&NR)	MSE(ME)	EFFECTS OF NR
t_0	1.5449	1.1083	0.4366
t_{ss1}	0.2643	0.1886	0.0757
t_{ss2}	0.2534	0.1808	0.0725
t_{a1}	0.2534	0.1808	0.0725
t_{a2}	0.2534	0.1808	0.0725
t_{a3}	0.2534	0.1808	0.0725
t_{p1}	0.0222	0.0172	0.005
t_{p2}	0.0236	0.0179	0.0057
t_{p3}	0.0314	0.0257	0.0057
t_{p4}	0.0323	0.0262	0.0061

Table 2: MSE of Existing and Proposed Estimators in presence of ME, and NR, and Effect of Non-response on the Estimators using population 2

Estimators	MSE (with ME&NR)	MSE (with ME)	EFFECTS OF NR
t_0	1.2175	1.1083	0.1092
t_{ss1}	0.2075	0.1886	0.0189
t_{ss2}	0.1989	0.1808	0.0181
t_{a1}	0.1989	0.1808	0.0181
t_{a2}	0.1989	0.1808	0.0181
t_{a3}	0.1989	0.1808	0.0181
t_{p1}	0.0186	0.0172	0.0014
t_{p2}	0.01941	0.0179	0.0015
t_{p3}	0.0274	0.0257	0.0017
t_{p4}	0.0280	0.0262	0.0018

Table 3: MSE of Existing and Proposed Estimators in presence of ME, and NR, and Effect of Non-response on the Estimators using population 3

Estimators	MSE (with ME&NR)	MSE (with ME)	EFFECTS OF NR
t_0	0.8875	0.3148	0.1913
t_{ss1}	0.6366	0.3987	0.0793
t_{ss2}	0.3377	0.0844	0.0885
t_{a1}	0.3377	0.0844	0.0885
t_{a2}	0.3377	0.0844	0.0885
t_{a3}	0.3377	0.0844	0.0885
t_{p1}	0.0192	0.0080	0.0073
t_{p2}	0.0266	0.0105	0.0088

t_{p3}	0.0037	0.0033	0.0059
t_{p4}	0.0082	0.0048	0.0068

Table 4: MSE of Existing and Proposed Estimators in presence of ME, and NR, and Effect of Non-response on the Estimators using population 4

Estimators	MSE(with ME&NR)	MSE (with ME)	EFFECTS OF NR
t_0	0.5057	0.3148	0.5727
t_{ss1}	0.4780	0.3987	0.2379
t_{ss2}	0.1729	0.0844	0.2533
t_{a1}	0.1729	0.0844	0.2533
t_{a2}	0.1729	0.0844	0.2533
t_{a3}	0.1729	0.0844	0.2533
t_{p1}	0.0153	0.0080	0.0112
t_{p2}	0.0193	0.0105	0.0161
t_{p3}	0.0092	0.0033	0.0004
t_{p4}	0.0116	0.0048	0.0034

Tables 1-4, show the results of the mean square errors of the existing and proposed estimators in the presence of Non-Response (NR) and Measurement Error (ME), and their mean square errors in the presence of Measurement Error (ME) only. The effects of Non-Response on the existing and the proposed estimators can also be observed from the tables above, this effects are obtained by subtracting the MSE with Measurement error (ME) only from MSE with Non-response (NR) and Measurement Error (ME). It can be observed that Non-Response have lesser effects on the proposed estimators as compared to the existing ones considered in this study. It can also be observed that the proposed estimators have minimum MSE in the simultaneous presence on Non-response and Measurement Error (ME) and in the presence of Measurement error (ME) only, this implies that the proposed estimators are more efficient than the existing estimators considered in this study.

5 Conclusion

In the present study, we have proposed mean estimators and study the effect of Non-Response on the estimators along with the existing estimators in the literature, we also derive the mean square error (MSE) of the proposed estimators in the simultaneous presence of Non-Response (NR) and Measurement error (ME), we conclude that the proposed estimators are more efficient in the presence of Non-Response and Measurement Error and in the presence of Measurement Error alone with the evidence of minimum mean square error (MSE). We also concluded that Non-Response have little effect or impact on the proposed estimators as compared to Hansen and Hurwitz (1946), Singh and Sharma (2015) and Audu et al. (2021) estimator. Hence, we recommend the proposed estimators for estimation of population mean of the study variable in the simultaneous presence of Non-Response and Measurement Errors and since the effect of Non-Response on the proposed estimators, they stand the chance of producing more reliable estimates than estimators of Hansen and Hurwitz (1946), Singh and Sharma (2015) and Audu et al. (2021).

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